

Research Article

Determination of the Nutritional and Anti-nutritional Compositions of Bitter Kola
(*Garcinia kola*)

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Abstract

*The nutritional and anti-nutritional compositions of *Garcinia kola* were determined using standard methods of the Association of Official Analytical Chemist (AOAC). The results revealed moisture (57.42 ± 0.04), dry matter (40.53 ± 0.02), crude fat (4.19 ± 0.35), crude protein (2.47 ± 0.09), ash (0.92 ± 0.004), and total carbohydrates, (26.49 ± 0.04) respectively. Fe was the most abundant element in *Garcinia kola* seed ($18.14 \text{ mg}100 \text{ g}^{-1}$), followed by K ($2.51 \text{ mg}100 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Also Co ($2.01 \text{ mg}100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and Zn ($2.31 \text{ mg}100 \text{ g}^{-1}$) were detected. Mn and Cu were available at low values. However, Cr was not detected (ND). The results of the preliminary photochemical screening of the extracts of bitter kola reveal the presence of bioactive substances. Results obtained were comparable to results obtained by other authors. From the parameters determined, it shows the sample can act as antioxidants, anticancer, anti viral, anti inflammatory, and anti allergic due to the results obtained.*

Keywords: Nutritional, Mineral, Antibiotics, Herbal, Stimulants, Medicinal, Toxicity, Constituents.

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Introduction

Garcinia kola (bitter kola) is a dicotyledonous plant having a place with the group of plant called Gutiferae. It is an enduring yield developing in the timberland, disseminated west and focal Africa (Iwu 1993). Bitter kola is a mainstream rural

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produce accessible in enormous amount in West Africa especially in Nigeria and it is a plant that develops in the rainforest. It is utilized widely in the readiness of natural medications either as energizer, supplement or as home grown cures also. Harsh kola has been recognized as a powerful anti-infection which could be compelling in the treatment of numerous maladies. It is assessed that over 70% of present day pharmaceutical items depend on herb. The natural product, seed, nuts, and bark of the plant have been utilized for quite a long time in medication to treat infirmity from hacks, fever, the runs, tuberculosis and other bacterial diseases. It assists with detoxifying the framework *Garcinia kola* plant is a plant inferred medication which has numerous advantages, for example, low harmfulness status/relative wellbeing, openness and reasonableness. Plant parts have been a wellspring of home grown medication which has been demonstrated to be powerful to about 80% of populace as essential medicinal services use (Igboko, 1983, Sodipo and Akiniyi, 2000).

Reports have been made by a few creators on severe kola, Dah-Nouvlessounon *et al.* (2015) announced healthful and hostile to supplement organization of three Kola nuts acquired in Benin, Akpakpan *et al.* (2020) wrote about phytochemical screening and explanatory evaluation of corrosive base pointer properties of red and white kola nuts concentrates, Adeniyi *et al.* (2017) looked into on the relative investigation of the proximate and unsaturated fat profiles of *Cola nitida*, *Cola acuminata* and *Garcinia kola*, Odebunmi *et al.* (2009) chipped away at the proximate and healthful structure of kola nut (*Cola nitida*), bitter cola (*Garcinia kola*) and crocodile pepper (*Aframomum melegueta*), while Onyekwelu *et al.* (2015) focused on cancer prevention agent, dietary and hostile to wholesome arrangement of *Garcinia kola* and *Chrysophyllum albidum* from rainforest biological system of Ondo State, Nigeria, however very little was done on the nourishing and antinutritional estimations of *Garcinia kola*. This work was set out upon to create more data on severe kola. In the light of this, the proximate, minerals, and phytochemical constituents of seeds of *Garcinia kola* got in Warri, Delta State, Nigeria were resolved.

Materials and Methods

The *Garcinia kola* (Bitter kola) were newly gathered and bought from neighborhood ranchers at the Warri showcase in Delta State, Nigeria. The *Garcinia kola* was enveloped by dry banana leaves (conventional technique) for 3 weeks. The dried (sun dried) seeds tests were ground utilizing research center mortar and pestle kept in a polythene sack and put away in hermetically sealed containers till investigations.

Proximate Content Determination

Standard methods of the Association of Official Analytical Chemist (AOAC, 1990) were used to determine the moisture, crude protein, crude fat, total ash and crude fiber

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contents of the sample. Moisture content was determined by heating 2.0g of each sample to a constant weight in a crucible placed in an oven maintained at 105° C. The dry matter was used in the determination of the other parameters. Crude protein (% total nitrogen x 6.25) was also determined by the Kjeldahl method, using 2.0g samples, crude fat were obtained by exhaustively extracting 5.0g of the sample in a soxhlet apparatus using petroleum boiling point range 40-60° C as the extract. Ash content was determined by the incineration of 10.0g samples placed in a muffle furnace maintained at 550° C for 5 h. Crude fiber was obtained by digesting 2.0g of samples with H₂SO₄ and NaOH and incinerating the residue in obtained a muffle furnace maintained at 550° C for 5 h, total carbohydrate was obtained by different method; each analysis was carried out in two places.

Mineral Content Determination

The mineral contents of sample were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Shimadzu AA-670) after dry ashing of the samples. The ash sample was transferred quantitatively into a conical flask and dissolved in 10 cm³ of 3% Ferric chloride and the mixture was heated on a hot plate, then filtered into a 100 cm³ volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water. The mineral contents (Potassium, Calcium, Magnesium, Iron, Zinc, Manganese and Phosphorus) of the solution were determined using atomic absorption spectrometer.

Data obtained were generated in triplicates and analyzed, using Minitab 16 Statistical Software.

Anti-nutrients

This aspect of analysis was performed qualitatively (Cannell, 1998)

Test for Tannins

About 0.5g of the ground sample of *Garcinia kola* was boiled in 20ml of water in a separate test tube and then filtered. A few drop of 0.1% FeCl₃ was added and observed for brownish green or blue black.

Test for Phlobatannin

An aqueous extract of the plant sample of *Garcinia kola* (bitter cola) was boiled with 1% aqueous HCl and deposition of a red precipitate was taken as evidence for the presence of phlobatannin.

Test for Saponins

The powdered sample *Garcinia kola* (2g) was boiled in 20ml of distilled water in a water bath and filtered. 10 cm³ of the filtrate was mixed with 5 cm³ of distilled water and shaken vigorously for a stable resistant froth. The frothing was mixed with 3 drops of olive oil, shaken vigorously and then observed for the formation of emulsion.

Test for Flavonoids

A 5 cm³ of 10% dilute ammonia solution was added to a portion of the aqueous filtrate of the extract, followed by addition of concentrated H₂SO₄. A yellow coloration observed indicated the presence of flavonoid.

Test for Cardiac Glycosides

A 5 cm³ of the extract was treated with 2 cm³ of glacial acetic acid containing 1 drop of FeCl₃ solution (0.1%). This was underlayered with 1ml of concentrated H₂SO₄. A brown ring of the interface indicates deoxysugar characteristics of cardenolides. A violet ring may appear below the brown ring, while in the acetic layer, a greenish ring may form just gradually throughout thin layer.

Preparation of Fat Free Samples

A 2 g of the sample were defatted with 100 cm³ of diethyl ether using a soxhlet apparatus for 2 h.

Determination of Total Phenols by Spectrometer Method

For the extraction of the phenolic component, the fat free samples of the plant were boiled with 25 cm³ of ether for 15 min. A 2.5 cm³ of the extract was pipetted into a 25 cm³ flask, and then 5 cm³ of distilled water was added to 1 cm³ of ammonium hydroxide solution and 2.5 cm³ of concentrated alcohol were also added. The sample was left to react for 30 min for colour development. The absorbance of the solution was read using a UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Mettler Toledo, Model UV 5) at 505 nm wave lengths as described by Obadoni and Ochuko (2001).

The results of the preliminary photochemical screening of the extracts of bitter kola reveal the presence of bioactive substances. Results obtained were comparable to results obtained by Faruq *et al.* (2004); Ogukwe *et al.* (2004); Akpan and Udoh (2004), and Abulude (2007) for extract of *Senna italica*, *Sansevieria trifasciata*, *Raphia hookeri*, and some woody plants leaves respectively.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Nutritional Composition (%) of *Garcinia kola*

Parameters	<i>Garcinia kola</i>
Moisture	57.42±0.04
Dry	40.53±0.02
Crude fat	4.19±0.35
Crude protein	2.47±0.09
Ash	0.92±0.004
Crude fibre	5.03±0.13
Total carbohydrate	26.49±0.64

Table 1 shows the moisture content to be 57.42 (%) and its dry matter was 40.53 %. The crude fat, crude protein, crude fiber, crude and total carbohydrate were 26.49, 4.19, 2.47, 5.03, 0.92, and 0.92 % respectively. These qualities are comparative from what had recently been accounted for *Garcinia kola* (Odebunmi *et al.*, 2009), they examined the proximate and wholesome organization of kolanut (*Cola nitida*), severe cola (*Garcinia kola*) and gator pepper (*Aframomu melegueta*) and announced a protein substance of 2.48%, fluid 4.51%, debris of 0.79% and rough strands substance of 5.23% in the seed and the report of Alaje *et al.* (2014). The shifting creation revealed by different examinations can be credited with season, condition and condition or time assessment.

Table 2: Mineral Composition of Seed sample (mg100 g⁻¹)

Mineral	Concentrations
Magnesium	0.42 ± 0.30
Calcium	1.86±0.42
Potassium	2.51±0.12
Phosphorous	0.33±0.10
Sodium	0.72±0.10
Iron	18.14±0.20
Zinc	2.31±0.01
Manganese	0.78±0.20
Copper	2.01±0.50
Chromium	ND
Cobalt	0.55±0.20
Cadmium	0.29±0.10

ND - Not Detectable

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Table 2 shows the consequences of the mineral piece. Fe was the most copious component accessible in *Garcinia kola* seed (18.14 mg100 g⁻¹), trailed by K (2.51 mg100 g⁻¹). Additionally Co (2.01 mg100 g⁻¹) and Zn (2.31 mg100 g⁻¹) were distinguished. Mn and Co were accessible at low qualities. Be that as it may, Cr was not identified in *Garcinia kola*. The aftereffects of the mineral organizations may demonstrate that severe kola are plentiful as far as mineral components. This becomes significant when minerals like P, Ca, Mg, K, Fe, and Zn are required in the body. The Zn substance could imply that the seeds can assume a significant job in the administration of diabetes, which results from insulin failing. Zn is fundamental for the creation of insulin, a hormone and carbonic anhydrase, a catalyst in the body (Okwu, 2004). Fe is a segment of hemoglobin. It enables oxygen to move, together with hemoglobin and ferrodizin, it assumes significant job in man's digestion (Okwu, 2004).

Clearly seed aggregates fundamental, significant, vital, valuable and accommodating components for plant, man and creatures. The nearness of Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Co³⁺, Cr³⁺, Cu²⁺, Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ reflects their capacity as fundamental supplement components, frequently as co-calculate activators metal-ligand compound edifices (Valkovic, 1975). Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ are present in replaceable sums and go about as restricting operators to meld the cell dividers together (Dser, 1979). The high grouping of specific metals, Mg²⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Fe²⁺ in the plants are basic for legitimate development and ordinary working of the plant (Underwood, 1971). Co³⁺, Cr²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ (Valkovic, 1975) are fundamental for hair development and for expanding the pace of milk creation by pregnant females.

In any case, the lower Na substance of *Garcinia kola* may be a favorable position because of the immediate relationship of sodium admission with hypertension in human (Dahl, 1972). *Garcinia kola* seeds are rich in phytonutrient, for example, flavonoids, phenolic compound, tannins, saponin, terpenoids, cardiovascular glycosides and alkaloids.

The organic elements of flavonoids incorporates insurance against platelet ulcers, infections, and tumors (Okwu, 2004). This might be the explanation for the utilization of concentrates of this plant in the treatment of intestinal difficulties in natural medication (Okwu and Omodamiro, 2005), the nearness of phenolic mixes in the seed of *Garcinia kola* shows that this plant may be an antimicrobial operator. This is on the grounds that phenols and phenolic mixes have been widely utilized in sanitization and remain the standard with which different bactericides are looked at. Phenolic mixes as electron benefactors are promptly oxidized from phenolate particle or quinine, an electron acceptor. This offers ascend to down to earth employments. Protonated phenol is utilized as cleaning specialist. Concentrates from *Garcinia kola* subsequently have strong

bactericidal properties (Okwu and Omodamiro, 2005). These discoveries upheld the utilization of concentrate from *Garcinia kola* in forestalling the arrangement of wound diseases and furthermore in treating wounds that not just recuperates quick (Okwu, 2004).

Phytochemicals have been found to restrain microbes, parasites, infections and bugs. The nearness of phytochemicals in the foundation of *Garcinia kola* might be liable for the antibacterial movement of the plant (Margorie, 1999), for example, the nearness of tannins in plants removes which is known to have antibacterial and antifungal properties may give the opportunity for customary specialists to utilize it as solutions for fever and cerebral pain, seizures and stomach issue.

This somewhat clarified the utilization of these seed materials in natural medication, as rich wellsprings of phytochemicals combined with the nearness of the fundamental nutrients and minerals. *Garcinia kola* seeds can be viewed as a potential wellspring of helpful nourishments and medications detailing. The employments of these plants for the treatment of the infection as guaranteed by customary healer are likewise being examined.

Conclusion

Garcinia kola is plentiful in supplement and mineral pieces. It very well may be of huge use in phytomedicine and can be remembered for medicinal services conveyance framework especially in the creating economy. It tends to be finished up from thiThis implies that residents of Burutu town are constantly faced with health risks associated with the consumption and utilization of contaminated water obtained from these sources.

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